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Research Article

**STUDY OF VITAMIN D DEFICIENCY IN HEPATITIS C VIRUS
INFECTION IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL LAHORE**¹Dr Ayesha Mubarik, ²Dr Farah Masood, ³Dr anwar ahmed¹Rashid Latif Medical Complex, Lahore., ²King Edward Medical Universty Lahore., ³muhammad medical college mirpur khas**Article Received:** September 2020 **Accepted:** October 2020 **Published:** November 2020**Abstract:**

In the past few years, a growing body of clinical evidence has highlighted the risk of vitamin D deficiency in patients with chronic hepatitis C and that vitamin D levels are associated with the course of hepatitis C virus (HCV) infection, adverse effects, and treatment response to peginterferon/ribavirin. Recently, studies have found that vitamin D status is related to drug resistance and increased risk of infection in patients with liver cirrhosis. Vitamin D-related gene polymorphisms have been found to explain the interactions between vitamin D deficiency and HCV infection, offering a new perspective toward understanding the current problems such as the development of insulin resistance and racial differences in sustained virological response. Studies have been conducted to determine whether vitamin D supplementation as an adjuvant yields a better result compared with traditional HCV treatment. Here, we provide a brief review of the past and present knowledge of vitamin D in HCV infection.

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INTRODUCTION:

More than 180 million people are estimated to be infected with the hepatitis C virus (HCV) worldwide; ~ 20% of those with chronic HCV infection progress to cirrhosis [1], and the median survival for HCV-infected patients who develop hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) is as short as 13.1 months from the time of HCC diagnosis [2]. HCV causes ~ 700 000 deaths annually [3]. Vitamin D is an important steroid hormone with pleiotropic effects and is known to play a key role in calcium and bone homeostasis. Most vitamin D is converted from 7-dehydrocholesterol (7-DHC) in the skin through sunlight, and then metabolized in the liver to 25-hydroxyvitamin D [25(OH)D], which is mediated by 25-hydroxylases, including the microsomal 25-hydroxylase (CYP2R1) and the mitochondrial cholesterol 27-hydroxylase (CYP27A1) enzymes. Finally, the biologically active agonist for vitamin D receptor (VDR), 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D₃ or calcitriol, is produced from circulating renal or extra-renal 25 (OH)D by 1 α -hydroxylase (CYP27B1); calcitriol is also highly bound to vitamin D-binding protein (DBP), which is also known as vitamin D-binding globulin (GC), and is the ligand that activates the VDR. Recently, evidence has emerged that vitamin D has antifibrotic, anti-inflammatory, and immunomodulatory properties. These extra skeletal effects are relevant in the pathogenesis and treatment of many causes of chronic liver disease. Vitamin D deficiency was observed in most hepatitis B virus-infected patients [4] and in patients with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease compared with healthy persons.

In fact, recent studies have found that vitamin D deficiency is also related to HCV progression [6–8], and the response to peginterferon/ribavirin (peg-IFN/RBV) therapy plays a role as a predictor of the response [6,9,10]. However, the current understanding of the pathogenic mechanisms underlying the high prevalence of vitamin D deficiency and the explanation of its effects in chronic hepatitis C (CHC) are insufficient. Neither an agreed upon definition of vitamin D deficiency nor an application standard of vitamin D supplementation has been established, especially in HCV-infected patients, and interactions between vitamin D and HCV are direct and indirect, which are far from complete to form a theoretical system. The purposes of this article are to discuss recent data on the role of vitamin D in HCV-infected patients.

Vitamin D deficiency in chronic hepatitis C infection:

Presently, vitamin D deficiency and insufficiency are seen among more than one-third of the adults worldwide [11–13]. The most recent consensus concerning hypovitaminosis D in the general population, according to the guideline of the Institute of Medicine's 2011 report, defined vitamin D deficiency as less 20 ng/ml [14], and the published Endocrine Society's Practice Guidelines [15] adopted vitamin D deficiency as less than 20 ng/ml, insufficiency as 21–29 ng/ml, and sufficiency as at least 30 ng/ml for maximum musculoskeletal health. The purported purpose of the guideline did not specifically consider diseased populations; thus, there still lacks an optimal and clinically relevant vitamin D level cut-off value to define the decrease of serum vitamin D levels in patients with CHC. Debate over what blood levels of 25(OH)D are considered deficient and sufficient continues. Simultaneously, almost more than 60% patients with HCV infection have hypovitaminosis D in different areas over the past decade, including Asia [16,17], Australia [18], Europe [6,9,19,20], and the USA [21,22]. In particular, previous reports have shown that African-Americans have significantly lower serum 25(OH)D levels than European Americans [23,24].

Vitamin D and hepatitis C virus-related fibrosis:

Over the past decade, many publications have assessed vitamin D status and fibrosis stage in CHC, but conflicting conclusions have been reached [6,19,25–28]. Several cross-sectional studies have been conducted, most of which have focused on genotype 1 patients, and low 25(OH)D levels were independently related to severe fibrosis [6,28]. Several studies did not find significant associations between vitamin D level and fibrosis [19,25–27]. Two were randomized controlled trials (RCTs), the largest of which included 516 patients living in France who were infected with genotype 1, and it found no effect of 25(OH)D on virological response or fibrosis progression upon receiving peg-IFN/RBV [27]; another cohort of 274 treatment-naïve patients with HCV-1 [26].

Furthermore, to detect the overall effects of vitamin D on populations with different genetic backgrounds, a recent meta-analysis involved 8321 HCV-infected patients from Europe, the USA, and Australia and showed an inverse association with the severity of liver fibrosis. However, the results from the odds ratio (OR) data extracted studies showed that there was no significant association between serum vitamin D status and the severity of liver fibrosis, although stratifying analyses were conducted by geographic region; the pooled ORs of the studies were 1.33 (95%CI: 0.35–5.08; P = 0.052; I² = 66.2%) for those conducted in the

USA and 0.88 (95%CI: 0.694–1.116; $P = 0.096$; $I^2 = 64.0\%$) for those conducted in Europe [8]. In contrast, to further investigate the relationship between vitamin D and liver fibrosis, a meta-analysis of hepatitis C-mono infected or HCV co-infected patients, including 2521 patients greater than or equal to 18 years old, found that nine of the 12 studies correlated advanced liver disease, defined as a Metavir value of F3/4, with 25(OH)D insufficiency (OR = 1.88; 95%CI: 1.27–2.77; $I^2 = 66.94\%$), thus indicating a significant association across studies [7].

Vitamin D and hepatitis C virus-related hepatocellular carcinoma:

Several studies have shown that vitamin D deficiency and sufficiency are associated with the presence of various types of cancer, including HCC [29,30]. Four independent cohorts of HCV-infected individuals, including 1279 white and Japanese CHC-infected patients with HCC and 4325 without HCC, were adopted to investigate the association between genetic variations in CYP2R1, DBP, and 7-dehydrocholesterol reductase (DHCR7) gene and HCV-induced HCC. In the combined analyses of these cohorts, the strongest associations were found with GC (OR = 1.56; 95%CI: 1.12–2.15; $P = 0.007$) and DHCR7 (OR = 1.42; 95%CI: 1.13–1.78; $P = 0.003$), whereas CYP2R1 was almost significantly associated with HCV-induced HCC (OR = 1.13; 95%CI: 0.99–1.28; $P = 0.07$), suggesting a causal role of vitamin D metabolism in HCV-induced HCC [31]. Population-based studies have been limited in investigating the relationship between HCC and vitamin D levels, and there is currently no published evidence that supplementation of vitamin D or its analogues translate into a benefit in HCV-infected patients with HCC.

Vitamin D and hepatitis C virus treatment:

Several factors likely affecting the response to pegIFN/ RBV therapy have been reported, including factors in both the virus and host, such as HCV genotype 1, male sex, human immunodeficiency virus and hepatitis B virus coinfection, advanced liver fibrosis, insulin resistance, and high viral load ($\geq 600\,000$ UI/ml) [32,33]. Since the first observation in 2010 that low vitamin D serum levels correlate with negative response to pegIFN/RBV-based therapy in genotype 1 chronic hepatitis C (G1CHC) [6], increasing studies have analysed the relationship between treatment response in CHC with vitamin D status, determining that they are not affected by hepatitis C genotype or geographical distribution.

Pre-treatment vitamin D deficiency is reportedly an independent predictor of failure to achieve a sustained virological response (SVR) in both HCV genotype 1 (HCV-1) and HCV-2/3 patients from Europe [6,9,10] and Asia [10,17] and HCV-4 patients from Africa [34], whereas other studies conducted mostly in HCV-1 patients found no clear association [20,22,26,27]. It is plausible that differences within the patient populations in each study could explain the discordant results.

The first meta-analysis of serum 25(OH)D levels and HCV infection summarized eleven studies, which included 1575 cases with hepatitis C; high rates of SVR were observed in HCV individuals with vitamin D levels above 30 ng/ml (OR = 1.57; 95%CI: 1.12–2.20; $P = 0.3799$; $I^2 = 6.5\%$) and those supplemented with vitamin D (OR = 4.59; 95%CI: 1.67–12.63; $P = 0.2395$; $I^2 = 30.0\%$), regardless of genotype [35]. To provide a further reliably quantified relationship, another meta-analysis was performed in 2014 [36] that showed an association between low vitamin D status and a lower odd of achieving SVR following pegIFN/RBV therapy in patients with CHC. However, in the same year, Kitson *et al.* [37] evaluated 11 studies comprising 2605 patients with chronic HCV infection and found no significant association between the baseline mean 25(OH)D level and SVR (OR = 1.44; 95% CI: 0.92–2.26; $P = 0.11$), regardless of genotype. In addition, it is controversial whether in African-Americans there exists an association between vitamin D concentrations and the possibility to attain SVR in individuals infected with HCV genotype 1 based on pegIFN/RBV therapy [22,38].

To date, only one study has evaluated this influence in patients with direct-acting antivirals (DAAs) treatment, but the results showed that vitamin D levels increased mildly but not significantly in all patients after DAAs treatment. Furthermore, neither the pre-treatment level nor the change in levels during DAAs therapy was associated with SVR [21].

Genetic influence explains vitamin D deficiency in patients with chronic hepatitis C infection

Cholesterol metabolism in the first step of vitamin D synthesis may be a possible cause of vitamin D deficiency. Lower baseline distal cholesterol and 7-DHC were found in patient with HCV-3 infection [39], which could be reversed after treatment with sofosbuvir and ribavirin [38], indicating that HCV-3 virus eradication may affect the cholesterol biosynthesis pathway. Furthermore, in 260 Italian

patients with G1CHC infection, the DHCR7 GG genotype was independently linked to lower vitamin D serum levels and more severe liver fibrosis [28]. A prospective cohort of 398 genotype 1-infected patients from Germany showed a higher prevalence of DHCR7 TT related to SVR [40]. Another study including 623 Thai patients also found an association with lower SVR rates compared with those with the DHCR7 TT/TG genotype, whereas the SVR rate did not differ in HCV non-genotype 1-infected patients [41].

A genetic influence in the second step was found in G1 HCV-infected patients from Germany, whereby polymorphisms of CYP27B1-1260, such as AA or CA genotype, were related to a higher SVR rate compared with those with the AC and CC genotype [42]. Meanwhile, in a cohort of 238 white patients with CHC infection treated with pegIFN/RBV, there was no correlation between CYP27B1-1260 rs10877012 polymorphism and response to therapy [43], which is in agreement with Thanapirom *et al.* [41].

In the final step, a genome-wide association study cohort of ~ 30 000 European individuals identified the GC variants associated with lower 25(OH)D concentrations and strongly correlated with lower levels of DBP [44], whereas no association was found between the polymorphisms of GC and treatment outcome, no matter the genotype, in a study of 623 Thai patients [41]. Recently, the first cross-sectional study on the quantitative hepatic expression of VDR in G1CHC reported that VDR expression was reduced according to the severity of liver fibrosis and necro-inflammatory activity after correcting for well-known metabolic and histological risk factors [45]. Garcia-Martin *et al.* [43] observed that the CCA haplotype and the carrier state of the VDR rs2228570 T allele were related to a higher probability of pegIFN/RBV therapy success in a cohort of 238 white patients with CHC infection. Similarly, the bAt (CCA) haplotype and ApaI CC genotype were associated with rapid fibrosis progression [46], and those carrying the bAt (CCA) haplotype, ApaI CC genotype, and TaqI AA genotype had a nonsignificant trend toward lower rates of achieving rapid virological response and SVR [47]

Furthermore, favourable VDR variants (rs7975232-C, rs2239185-T, and rs11574129-T) might contribute to decreased susceptibility to HCV infection in a high-risk HCV genotype 1-infected Chinese population [48].

However, it is worth noting that, based on pegIFN/RBV therapy combined with a protease inhibitor, Arai *et al.* [49] showed a different result in

that none of the vitamin D-related gene polymorphisms GC (rs2282679), DHCR7 (rs7944926), CYP2R1 (rs10741657), CYP27B1 (rs10877012), and VDR gene (rs2228570) had an effect on serum 25(OH)D3 levels in 177 genotype 1b-infected CHC patients from Japan. This might be owing to a higher treatment response of the protease inhibitor that covered up the role of vitamin D-related gene polymorphisms. Above all, these studies may offer a potential mechanism of vitamin D deficiency and its role in influencing the treatment response in HCV-infected patients (Table 1). model of assessment for insulin resistance index. The GC1s/ GC1s phenotype variant of DBP was found to be a risk factor of insulin resistance in a CHC group containing 85.5% genotype 1 (mostly 1b) [51], and CYP27B1-1260 genotype appeared to have an increased risk of developing abnormal fasting plasma glucose levels [52]. Therefore, the determinants of vitamin D may contribute to the development of insulin resistance in HCV-infected patients. Furthermore, African-American patients with HCV-1 infection attained SVR at only approximately one-half the rate of whites after pegIFN/RBV treatment, and it was found that the former expressed a high-affinity variant (the GC1f protein isoform expressed from the rs7041T/rs4588C allele) rather than lower-affinity variants (the GC1s and GC2 isoforms), whereas most white Americans did not [53]. The GC1f allele was also found to be a risk factor of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease compared with the GC1s allele [54]. Whether such racial differences in vitamin D physiology are associated with the achievement of SVR has not been studied yet.

Potential mechanisms for the hypothesized link between vitamin D and hepatitis C virus infection:

In-vitro studies have been conducted to evaluate the antiviral effect of vitamin D. In Huh7.5 hepatoma cells, biological evidence demonstrated for the first time that the level of 1,25 (OH)2D3 directly suppresses HCV-RNA replication in a dose-dependent manner through increased expression of interferon- β (IFN- β) and the IFN-stimulated gene MxA [55]; in specific HCV genotype 1b or 2a replicons, 1,25(OH)2D3 and its receptor VDR were modulators of IFN- β -induced signalling through the Jak-STAT pathway, which provides a dynamic and tissue-specific or cell-specific method of controlling IFN- β signalling [56]. Furthermore, it is known that DAAs play their roles through the non-structural protein (NS) 3/NS4A protease and NS5A and NS5B polymerase inhibitors, and 25(OH)D3 was found to have a direct antiviral effect by inhibiting the virus assembly step and perhaps by targeting NS3-4A, influencing the

steps of HCV entry and replication [57]. Patients whose vitamin D levels were below 20 ng/ml were more likely to have pre-existing Y93 RAVs (drug resistance-associated variants) at the HCV NS5A

region [58], and patients who developed NS5A multi-RAVs were likely to fail to respond to sofosbuvir/ledipasvir therapy [59].

Table 1. Vitamin D-related gene polymorphisms influence sustained virological response in patients with chronic hepatitis C infection

Factors	Country	Patients	References
DHCR7	Germany	398 G1CHC	Grammatikos et al. [40]
	Thailand	623 G1CHC	Thanapirom et al. [41]
CYP27B1-1260	Germany	468 HCV-1, HCV-2, HCV-3	Lange et al. [42]
	Spain	238 CHC	Garcia-Martin et al. [43]
	Thailand	G1CHC and non-G1CHC	Thanapirom et al. [41]
GC	Thailand	G1CHC and non-G1CHC	Thanapirom et al. [41]
CYP2R1	Thailand	G1CHC and non-G1CHC	Thanapirom et al. [41]
VDR	Germany	CHC	Garcia-Martin et al. [43]
	China	139 G1CHC	Hung et al. [47]

CHC, chronic hepatitis C; HCV, hepatitis C virus; VDR, vitamin D receptor

Studies have identified the serum levels of IFN- γ inducible protein-10 (IP-10), also called CXC motif chemokine 10 (CXCL-10), and of the enzyme dipeptidyl peptidase-IV (DPP IV) as markers involved in inflammatory responses and predictors of treatment outcome in CHC [60–62]. Higher levels of CXCL-10 and activity of DPP IV predicted poorer outcomes. CXCL chemokines primarily attract Th1 lymphocytes and neutrophils, and CXC receptors are found predominantly on Th1 lymphocytes [63]; thus, IP-10 is a key chemokine in inflammation that selectively recruits Th1 lymphocytes into tissues [64]. It has been reported that carcinogenesis may occur in patients with chronic HCV infection with an increased level of Th2 cells, losing the dominance of Th1 cells [65]. Furthermore, vitamin D significantly suppresses the expression of Th1-associated IP-10 in a dose-dependent manner in patients with asthma [66] and increases the angiogenic capacity of myeloid angiogenic cells by down-regulating CXCL-10 in systemic lupus erythematosus [67].

In patients with CHC treated with vitamin D, pegylated IFN/ribavirin showed significant reduction of serum IP-10 within 4 weeks of treatment and lower IFN stimulating gene mRNA expression in hepatocytes compared with the control arm without

vitamin D [68]. Recently, a randomized double-blinded, placebo-control trial in Thailand observed a significant reduction of IP-10 and DPP IV levels compared with the placebo group upon correction of vitamin D deficiency in patients with CHC within 6 weeks without the influence of IFN, whereas the serum levels of Th1-related and Th2-related cytokines remained unchanged [62]. Further investigations are required to reveal the relationships between CXCL-10/IP-10 and Th1/Th2 cells in HCV-infected patients.

Oxidative stress has been proposed as a key step in the development and progression of liver damage. In 2010, experimental models showed that vitamin D, via its interaction with the VDR, protects against oxidative stress

[69]. Recently, a study from Iran showed the relationship between hypovitaminosis D and oxidative stress in patients with HCV through a higher oxidant stress index, advanced oxidation protein products, and NOx levels, which are oxidative stress markers [70], and similar results were also observed in Brazil, Japan, and Egypt [71–73].

Vitamin D supplementation: a supplement to ongoing therapy for hepatitis C virus infection:

In biological studies, vitamin D supplementation showed its ability to improve SVR in 1b patients whether they were treatment-naïve [74] or with refractory factors based on simeprevir with pegIFN/RBV from a RCT [75]. A cross-sectional study of 108 Spanish genotype 1 patients with CHC found that vitamin D deficiency was common in patients but was not related to virological variables and also had no effect on HCV-RNA serum levels [19]. Vitamin D supplementation was also related to higher SVR rates in HCV-infected individuals (OR = 4.59; 95% CI: 1.67–12.63), regardless of genotype, where the highest level was observed among genotype 1 HCV-infected individuals [35]. No adverse events related to vitamin D supplementation were observed during the study period (6 weeks) in all patients [62], but it is unknown whether there could be related risks in the future. However, a prospective, randomized controlled, open-labelled, two group assignment study consisting of 101 chronic HCV-4 Egyptian patients found that vitamin D supplementation showed no effect on SVR [76]. A recent meta-analysis of Kim *et al.* [77] confirmed an improved effect on SVR rates of vitamin D supplementation in combination with conventional antiviral therapy in patients with CHC infection. It is interesting that a vitamin D RCT in patients with cirrhosis showed that vitamin D supplementation in patients with cirrhosis is as effective as in the general population, considering the vitamin D doses needed to achieve certain target levels of 25(OH)D [78]. However, more RCTs and meta-analyses are highly needed to better understand the total effect of vitamin D supplementation.

In summary, vitamin D can easily be supplemented and plays a role as a pre-treatment predictor of SVR to standard therapy, with infrequent adverse effects and few costs. However, consensus is still missing on optimal 25(OH)D target levels and dosing strategies. The doses adopted for vitamin D supplementation mainly vary from 1000 to 2000 IU/day [10,17,74,75]. Drug administration intervals, which influence drug effects, also need to be considered [79], as no study has examined this factor or set up different drug intervals. Furthermore, the form of administration mainly refers to 25(OH)D₃, although there are other types, such as cholecalciferol, a nonactivated vitamin-D₃ supplement, and alfa-calcidol, an activated 1(OH)D₃, showing similar results as 25(OH)D combined with SVR to pegIFN/ RBV therapy [72,80,81]. There have been few studies comparing the strength of the effect of various forms adopted for vitamin D [72].

CONCLUSION:

The adjunction of new direct antiviral agents is changing the therapeutic approach in chronic HCV infection. However, many patients are treated with the classic combination therapy of pegIFN/RBV where these new therapies cannot be afforded. One of the most important targets is to obtain SVR after treatment, which is associated with reduced HCC at any stage of fibrosis among HCV-infected persons [11]. With this standard of care, SVR is achieved in ~ 80% of patients with HCV genotypes 2 and 3. However, only half of patients with HCV genotype 1 responded to the treatment. In the quest to enhance treatment response, there has been significant interest in the association of serum 25-vitamin D levels and supplementation during the natural history and treatment of chronic HCV infection. Even in the era of DAAs, we should consider supplementation with vitamin D deficiency for patients with CHC infection.

Recommendations:

Although, recent findings showed the relationship between vitamin D and HCV infection, which comes first? What is the difference in the regulation of vitamin D in patients with CHC infection? How does one make clear guidelines for correcting vitamin D deficiency? Additional clinical data from large and well-defined patient cohorts is also required to verify the safety and efficacy of nutritional vitamin D therapy in this unique patient population and also as a strategy for physicians, medical specialists, and healthcare policy makers.

REFERENCES:

1. Antonelli A, Pistello M. New therapies, markers and therapeutic targets in HCV chronic infection, and HCV extrahepatic manifestations. *Curr Drug Targets* 2015; 18:752–755.
2. Moore MS, Ivanina E, Bornschlegel K, Qiao B, Schymura MJ, Laraque F. Hepatocellular carcinoma and viral hepatitis in New York City. *Clin Infect Dis* 2016; 63:1577–1583.
3. Lanini S, Easterbrook PJ, Zumla A, Ippolito G. Hepatitis C: global epi-demiology and strategies for control. *Clin Microbiol Infect* 2016; 22:833–838.
4. Hoan NX, Khuyen N, Binh MT, Giang DP, van Tong H, Hoan PQ, *et al.* Association of vitamin D deficiency with hepatitis B virus-related liver diseases. *BMC Infect Dis* 2016; 16:507.
5. Wang D, Lin H, Xia M, Aleteng Q, Li X, Ma H, *et al.* Vitamin D levels are inversely associated with liver fat content and risk of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease in a Chinese middle-aged and elderly population: the Shanghai Changfeng study. *PLoS ONE* 2016; 11:e0157515.

6. Petta S, Camma C, Scazzone C, Tripodo C, Di Marco V, Bono A, et al. Low vitamin D serum level is related to severe fibrosis and low responsiveness to interferon-based therapy in genotype 1 chronic hepatitis C. *Hepatology* 2010; 51:1158–1167.
7. Dadabhai AS, Saberi B, Lobner K, Shinohara RT, Mullin GE. Influence of vitamin D on liver fibrosis in chronic hepatitis C: a systematic review and meta-analysis of the pooled clinical trials data. *World J Hepatol* 2017; 9:278–287.
8. Luo YQ, Wu XX, Ling ZX, Cheng YW, Yuan L, Xiang C. Association between serum vitamin D and severity of liver fibrosis in chronic hepatitis C patients: a systematic meta-analysis. *J Zhejiang Univ Sci B* 2014; 15:900–906.
9. Gerova DI, Galunska BT, Ivanova II, Kotzev IA, Tchervenkov TG, Balev SP, Svinarov DA. Prevalence of vitamin D deficiency and insufficiency in Bulgarian patients with chronic hepatitis C viral infection. *Scand J Clin Lab Invest* 2014; 74:665–672.
10. Abu-Mouch S, Fireman Z, Jarchovsky J, Zeina AR, Assy N. Vitamin D supplementation improves sustained virologic response in chronic hepatitis C (genotype 1)-naive patients. *World J Gastroenterol* 2011; 17:5184–5190.
11. Sarafin K, Durazo-Arvizu R, Tian L, Phinney KW, Tai S, Camara JE, et al. Standardizing 25-hydroxyvitamin D values from the Canadian Health Measures Survey. *Am J Clin Nutr* 2015; 102:1044–1050.
12. Cashman KD, Dowling KG, Skrabakova Z, Gonzalez-Gross M, Valtrueña J, Henauw SD, et al. Vitamin D deficiency in Europe: pan-demic? *Am J Clin Nutr* 2016; 103:1033–1044.
13. Chen J, Yun C, He Y, Piao J, Yang L, Yang X. Vitamin D status among the elderly Chinese population: a cross-sectional analysis of the 2010-2013 China national nutrition and health survey (CNNHS). *Nutr J* 2017; 16:3.
14. Ross AC, Manson JE, Abrams SA, Aloia JF, Brannon PM, Clinton SK, et al. The 2011 report on dietary reference intakes for calcium and vitamin D from the Institute of Medicine: what clinicians need to know. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* 2011; 96:53–58.
15. Hossein-nezhad A, Holick MF. Optimize dietary intake of vitamin D: an epigenetic perspective. *Curr Opin Clin Nutr Metab Care* 2012; 15:567–579.
16. Huang J-F, Ko Y-M, Huang C-F, Yeh ML, Dai CY, Hsieh MH, et al. 25-Hydroxy vitamin D suppresses hepatitis C virus replication and contributes to rapid virological response of treatment efficacy. *Hepatol Res* 2017; 47:1383–1389.
17. Nimer A, Mouch A. Vitamin D improves viral response in hepatitis C genotype 2-3 naive patients. *World J Gastroenterol* 2012; 18:800–805.
18. Kitson MT, Roberts SK. D-livering the message: the importance of vitamin D status in chronic liver disease. *J Hepatol* 2012; 57:897–909.
19. Ladero JM, Torrejon MJ, Sanchez-Pobre P, Suárez A, Cuenca F, de la Orden V, et al. Vitamin D deficiency and vitamin D therapy in chronic hepatitis C. *Ann Hepatol* 2013; 12:199–204.
20. Melo-Villar L, Lampe E, de Almeida AJ, de Scalioni L, Lewis-Ximenez LL, Miguel JC, et al. Hypovitaminosis D and its relation to demographic and laboratory data among hepatitis C patients. *Ann Hepatol* 2015; 14:457–463.
21. Backstedt D, Pedersen M, Choi M, Seetharam A. 25-Vitamin D levels in chronic hepatitis C infection: association with cirrhosis and sustained virologic response. *Ann Gastroenterol* 2017; 30:344–348.
22. Weintraub SJ, Fleckenstein JF, Marion TN, Madey MA, Mahmoudi TM, Schechtman KB. Vitamin D and the racial difference in the genotype 1 chronic hepatitis C treatment response. *Am J Clin Nutr* 2012; 96:1025–1031.
23. Benjamin A, Moriakova A, Akhter N, Rao D, Xie H, Kukreja S, Barengolts E. Determinants of 25-hydroxyvitamin D levels in African-American and Caucasian male veterans. *Osteoporos Int* 2009; 20:1795–1803.
24. Murphy AB, Kelley B, Nyame YA, Martin IK, Smith DJ, Castaneda L, et al. Predictors of serum vitamin D levels in African American and European American men in Chicago. *Am J Mens Health* 2012; 6:420–426.
25. Ren Y, Liu M, Zhao J, Ren F, Chen Y, Li JF, et al. Serum vitamin D(3) does not correlate with liver fibrosis in chronic hepatitis C. *World J Gastroenterol* 2015; 21:11152–11159.
26. Kitson MT, Dore GJ, George J, Button P, McCaughan GW, Crawford DH, et al. Vitamin D status does not predict sustained virologic response or fibrosis stage in chronic hepatitis C genotype 1 infection. *J Hepatol* 2013; 58:467–472.
27. Belle A, Gizard E, Conroy G, Lopez A, Bouvier-Alias M, Rouanet S, et al. 25-OH vitamin D level has no impact on the efficacy of antiviral therapy in naive genotype 1 HCV-infected patients. *United European Gastroenterol J* 2017; 5:69–75.
28. Petta S, Grimaudo S, Marco VD, Scazzone C, Macaluso FS, Cammà C, et al. Association of

- vitamin D serum levels and its common genetic determinants, with severity of liver fibrosis in genotype 1 chronic hepatitis C patients. *J Viral Hepat* 2013; 20:486–493.
29. Holick MF. Vitamin D deficiency. *N Engl J Med* 2007; 357:266–281.
30. Rosen CJ. Clinical practice. Vitamin D insufficiency. *N Engl J Med* 2011; 364:248–254.
31. Lange CM, Miki D, Ochi H, Nischalke HD, Bojunga J, Bibert S, et al. Genetic analyses reveal a role for vitamin D insufficiency in HCV-associated hepatocellular carcinoma development. *PLoS ONE* 2013; 8: e64053.
32. Ghany MG, Strader DB, Thomas DL, Seeff LB. Diagnosis, management, and treatment of hepatitis C: an update. *Hepatology* 2009; 49:1335–1374.
33. Seeff LB, Hoofnagle JH. Appendix: The National Institutes of Health Consensus Development Conference Management of Hepatitis C 2002. *Clin Liver Dis* 2003; 7:261–287.
34. Abdelsalam A, Rashed L, Salman T, Hammad L, Sabry D. Molecular assessment of vitamin D receptor polymorphism as a valid predictor to the response of interferon/ribavirin-based therapy in Egyptian patients with chronic hepatitis C. *J Dig Dis* 2016; 17:547–553.
35. Villar LM, Antonio Del Campo J, Ranchal I, Lampe E, Romero-Gomez M. Association between vitamin D and hepatitis C virus infection: a meta-analysis. *World J Gastroenterol* 2013; 19:5917–5924.
36. Garcia-Alvarez M, Pineda-Tenor D, Jimenez-Sousa MA, Fernandez-Rodriguez A, Guzman-Fulgencio M, Resino S. Relationship of vitamin D status with advanced liver fibrosis and response to hepatitis C virus therapy: a meta-analysis. *Hepatology* 2014; 60:1541–1550.
37. Kitson MT, Sarrazin C, Toniutto P, Eslick GD, Roberts SK. Vitamin D level and sustained virologic response to interferon-based antiviral therapy in chronic hepatitis C: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Hepatol* 2014; 61:1247–1252.
38. Younossi ZM, Stepanova M, Estep M, Negro F, Clark PJ, Hunt S, et al. Dysregulation of distal cholesterol biosynthesis in association with relapse and advanced disease in CHC genotype 2 and 3 treated with sofosbuvir and ribavirin. *J Hepatol* 2016; 64:29–36.
39. Clark PJ, Thompson AJ, Vock DM, Kratz LE, Tolun AA, Muir AJ, et al. Hepatitis C virus selectively perturbs the distal cholesterol synthesis pathway in a genotype-specific manner. *Hepatology* 2012; 56:49–56.
40. Grammatikos G, Lange C, Susser S, Schwendy S, Dikopoulos N, Buggisch P, et al. Vitamin D levels vary during antiviral treatment but are unable to predict treatment outcome in HCV genotype 1 infected patients. *PLoS ONE* 2014; 9:e87974.
41. Thanapirom K, Suksawatamnuay S, Sukeepaisarnjaroen W, Tangkijvanich P, Treeprasertsuk S, Thaimai P, et al. Vitamin D-related gene polymorphism predict treatment response to pegylated interferon-based therapy in Thai chronic hepatitis C patients. *BMC Gastroenterol* 2017; 17:54.
42. Lange CM, Bojunga J, Ramos-Lopez E, von Wagner M, Hassler A, Vermehren J, et al. Vitamin D deficiency and a CYP27B1-1260 promoter polymorphism are associated with chronic hepatitis C and poor response to interferon-alfa based therapy. *J Hepatol* 2011; 54:887–893.
43. Garcia-Martin E, Agundez JA, Maestro ML, Suárez A, Vidaurreta M, Martínez C, et al. Influence of vitamin D-related gene polymorphisms (CYP27B and VDR) on the response to interferon/ribavirin therapy in chronic hepatitis C. *PLoS ONE* 2013; 8:e74764.
44. Wang TJ, Zhang F, Richards JB, Kestenbaum B, van Meurs JB, Berry D, et al. Common genetic determinants of vitamin D insufficiency: a genome-wide association study. *Lancet* 2010; 376:180–188.
45. Petta S, Grimaudo S, Tripodo C, Cabibi D, Calvaruso M, Di Cristina A, et al. The hepatic expression of vitamin D receptor is inversely associated with the severity of liver damage in genotype 1 chronic hepatitis C patients. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* 2015; 100:193–200.
46. Baur K, Mertens JC, Schmitt J, Iwata R, Stieger B, Eloranta JJ, et al. Combined effect of 25-OH vitamin D plasma levels and genetic vitamin D receptor (NR 111) variants on fibrosis progression rate in HCV patients. *Liver Int* 2012; 32:635–643.
47. Hung C-H, Hu T-H, Lu S-N, Chen C-H, Wang J-H, Lee C-M. Association of vitamin D receptor gene polymorphisms with response to peginterferon plus ribavirin in Asian patients with chronic hepatitis C. *J Formos Med Assoc* 2016; 115:278–283.
48. Wu M, Yue M, Huang P, Zhang Y, Xie C, Yu R, et al. Vitamin D level and vitamin D receptor genetic variations contribute to HCV infection susceptibility and chronicity in a Chinese population. *Infect Genet Evol* 2016; 41:146–152.

49. Arai T, Atsukawa M, Tsubota A, Kondo C, Shimada N, Abe H, et al. Vitamin D-related gene polymorphisms do not influence the outcome and serum vitamin D level in pegylated interferon/ribavirin therapy combined with protease inhibitor for patients with genotype 1b chronic hepatitis C. *J Med Virol* 2015; 87:1904–1912.
50. Lecube A, Hernandez C, Genesca J, Esteban JI, Jardi R, Simo R. High prevalence of glucose abnormalities in patients with hepatitis C virus infection: a multivariate analysis considering the liver injury. *Diabetes Care* 2004; 27:1171–1175.
51. Mateos-Munoz B, Garcia-Martin E, Torrejon MJ, Devesa-Medina MJ, Esguevillas G, Cárdenas MC, et al. GC gene polymorphism and unbound serum retinol-binding protein 4 are related to the risk of insulin resistance in patients with chronic hepatitis C: a prospective cross-sectional study. *Medicine* 2016; 95:e3019.
52. Sun D, Qi W, Wang S, Wang X, Zhang Y, Wang J. Genetic poly-morphism of CYP27B1-1260 as associated with impaired fasting glu-cose in patients with chronic hepatitis C undergoing antiviral therapy. *Hepat Mon* 2016; 16:e35179.
53. Chun RF, Lauridsen AL, Suon L, Zella LA, Pike JW, Modlin RL, et al. Vitamin D-binding protein directs monocyte responses to 25-hydroxy-and 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* 2010; 95:3368–3376.
54. Horita N, Miyazawa N, Tomaru K, Inoue M, Ishigatsubo Y, Kaneko T. Vitamin D binding protein genotype variants and risk of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: a meta-analysis. *Respirology* 2015; 20:219–225.
55. Gal-Tanamy M, Bachmetov L, Ravid A, Koren R, Erman A, Tur-Kaspa R, Zemel R. Vitamin D: an innate antiviral agent suppressing hepatitis C virus in human hepatocytes. *Hepatology* 2011; 54: 1570–1579.
56. Lange CM, Gouttenoire J, Duong FH, Morikawa K, Heim MH, Moradpour D. Vitamin D receptor and Jak-STAT signaling crosstalk results in calcitriol-mediated increase of hepatocellular response to IFN-alpha. *J Immunol (Baltimore, Md: 1950)* 2014; 192:6037–6044.
57. Matsumura T, Kato T, Sugiyama N, Tasaka-Fujita M, Murayama A, Masaki T, et al. 25-Hydroxyvitamin D3 suppresses hepatitis C virus production. *Hepatology* 2012; 56:1231–1239.
58. Okubo T, Atsukawa M, Tsubota A, Shimada N, Abe H, Yoshizawa K, et al. Association between vitamin D deficiency and pre-existing resistance-associated hepatitis C virus NS5A variants. *Hepatol Res* 2017; 47:641–649.
59. Kan H, Imamura M, Kawakami Y, Daijo K, Teraoka Y, Honda F, et al. Emergence of drug resistance-associated variants and changes in serum lipid profiles in sofosbuvir plus ledipasvir-treated chronic hepatitis C patients. *J Med Virol* 2017; 89:1963–1972.
60. Fattovich G, Covolo L, Bibert S, Askarieh G, Lagging M, Clément S, et al. IL28B polymorphisms, IP-10 and viral load predict virological response to therapy in chronic hepatitis C. *Aliment Pharmacol Ther* 2011; 33:1162–1172.
61. Casrouge A, Decalf J, Ahloulay M, Lababidi C, Mansour H, Vallet-Pichard A, et al. Evidence for an antagonist form of the chemokine CXCL10 in patients chronically infected with HCV. *J Clin Invest* 2011; 121:308–317.
62. Komolmit P, Charoensuk K, Thanapirom K, Suksawatamnuay S, Thaimai P, Chirathaworn C, Poovorawan Y. Correction of vitamin D deficiency facilitated suppression of IP-10 and DPP IV levels in patients with chronic hepatitis C: a randomised double-blinded, placebo-control trial. *PLoS One* 2017; 12:4.
63. Cassatella MA, Gasperini S, Calzetti F, Bertagnin A, Luster AD, McDonald PP. Regulated production of the interferon-gamma-inducible protein-10 (IP-10) chemokine by human neutrophils. *Eur J Immunol* 1997; 27:111–115.
64. Bonecchi R, Bianchi G, Bordignon PP, D'Ambrosio D, Lang R, Borsatti A, et al. Differential expression of chemokine receptors and chemotactic responsiveness of type 1 T helper cells (Th1s) and Th2s. *J Exp Med* 1998; 187:129–134.
65. Matsui T, Nagai H, Sumino Y, Miki K. Relationship of peripheral blood CD4-positive T cells to carcinogenesis in patients with HCV-related chronic hepatitis and liver cirrhosis. *Cancer Chemother Pharmacol* 2008; 62:401–406.
66. Kuo YT, Kuo CH, Lam KP, Chu YT, Wang WL, Huang CH, Hung CH. Effects of vitamin D3 on expression of tumor necrosis factor-alpha and chemokines by monocytes. *J Food Sci* 2010; 75:H200–H204.
67. Reynolds JA, Haque S, Williamson K, Ray DW, Alexander MY, Bruce IN. Vitamin D improves endothelial dysfunction and restores myeloid angiogenic cell function via reduced CXCL-10 expression in systemic lupus erythematosus. *Sci Rep* 2016; 6:22341.
68. Kondo Y, Kato T, Kimura O, Iwata T, Ninomiya M, Kakazu E, et al. 1(OH) vitamin D3 supplementation improves the sensitivity of the immune-response during Peg-IFN/RBV therapy

- in chronic hepatitis C patients-case controlled trial. PLoS ONE 2013; 8:e63672.
69. Hewison M. Vitamin D and the immune system: new perspectives on an old theme. *Endocrinol Metab Clin North Am* 2010; 39:365–379.
 70. Khadem Ansari MH, Omrani MD, Kheradmand F. Oxidative stress response in patients infected by diverse hepatitis C virus genotypes. *Hepat Mon* 2015; 15:e22069.
 71. de Almeida JP, Liberatti LS, Barros FE, Kallaur AP, Lozovoy MA, Scavuzzi BM, et al. Profile of oxidative stress markers is dependent on vitamin D levels in patients with chronic hepatitis C. *Nutrition* 2016; 32:362–367.
 72. Omori-Mizuno Y, Nakayama N, Inao M, Funyu J, Asabe S, Tomita K, et al. Randomized study comparing vitamin D3 and 1alpha-Hydroxyvitamin D3 in combination with pegylated interferon/ribavirin therapy for chronic hepatitis C. *J Gastroenterol Hepatol* 2015; 30:1384–1390.
 73. Gabr SA, Alghadir AH, Allam AA, Ajarem J, Al-Basher G, Abdel-Maksoud MA, et al. Correlation between vitamin D levels and apoptosis in geriatric patients infected with hepatitis C virus genotype 4. *Clin Interv Aging* 2016; 11:523–533.
 74. Yokoyama S, Takahashi S, Kawakami Y, Hayes CN, Kohno H, Kohno H, et al. Effect of vitamin D supplementation on pegylated interferon/ribavirin therapy for chronic hepatitis C genotype 1b: a randomized controlled trial. *J Viral Hepat* 2014; 21:348–356.
 75. Atsukawa M, Tsubota A, Shimada N, Yoshizawa K, Abe H, Asano T, et al. Effect of native vitamin D3 supplementation on refractory chronic hepatitis C patients in simeprevir with pegylated interferon/ribavirin. *Hepatol Res* 2016; 46:450–458.
 76. Esmat G, El Raziky M, Elsharkawy A, Sabry D, Hassany M, Ahmed A, et al. Impact of vitamin D supplementation on sustained virological response in chronic hepatitis C genotype 4 patients treated by pegylated interferon/ribavirin. *J Interferon Cytokine Res* 2015; 35:49–54.
 77. Kim HB, Myung SK, Lee YJ, Park BJ. Efficacy of vitamin D supplementation in combination with conventional antiviral therapy in patients with chronic hepatitis C infection: a meta-analysis of randomised controlled trials. *J Hum Nutr Diet* 2017; 31:168–177.
 78. Pilz S, Putz-Bankuti C, Gaksch M, Spindelboeck W, Haselberger M, Rainer F, et al. Effects of vitamin D supplementation on serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D concentrations in cirrhotic patients: a randomized controlled trial. *Nutrients* 2016; 8:5.
 79. Hollis BW, Wagner CL. Clinical review: The role of the parent compound vitamin D with respect to metabolism and function: Why clinical dose intervals can affect clinical outcomes. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* 2013; 98:4619–4628.
 80. Bitetto D, Fabris C, Fornasiere E, Pipan C, Fumolo E, Cussigh A, et al. Vitamin D supplementation improves response to antiviral treatment for recurrent hepatitis C. *Transpl Int* 2011; 24:43–50.
 81. Atsukawa M, Tsubota A, Shimada N, Kondo C, Itokawa N, Nakagawa A, et al. Efficacy of alfacalcidol on PEG-IFN/ribavirin combination therapy for elderly patients with chronic hepatitis C: a pilot study. *Hepat Mon* 2013; 13:e14872.